

Supplemental Material: Model-free data-efficient inference of network connectivity from time series with subReservoir Computing

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Link classification

Existing classification algorithms can be applied to estimate a suitable threshold T from bimodal distributions. Otsu's method is a non-parametric technique used in image processing to binarize gray-scale images by separating pixels into two classes, according to their intensity¹. It defines the threshold as the value that minimizes intra-class variance or, equivalently, maximizes inter-class variance. Bimodal distributions can be represented as a Gaussian mixture model². The idea is to find the parameters of normal distributions that, combined, would best describe the observations. Once the parameters for each distribution (mean, standard deviation, number of samples) are known, the threshold can be computed. Related clustering methods, such as density-based clustering^{3?} and k -means^{??} are also suitable to separate clusters of points.

We propose here a simple method that is based on partitioning the set of values $A_{i,j}$ (the samples) into equal parts by finding the corresponding quantiles. Then we compute the difference between consecutive quantiles, which is expected to be higher when there are fewer samples. We then detect the local maxima and select them as candidates for threshold. The only parameter in this method is the number of quantile values to be

computed. This number can be arbitrary, depending on the desired precision, but the smoothness of the resulting curve in the difference depends on the number of samples. Our tests indicate that around 30 points suffice for distributions with a wide range of number of samples. We demonstrate the method of differences of quantiles on a synthetic example in Figure 1. In this example, we generated a population of samples by combining two sub-populations drawn from normal distributions with different mean values. The differences of quantiles peak at the value that intuitively separates both clusters.

Figure 1 Demonstration on synthetic data of the method of differences of quantiles. We generated a synthetic population of 30000 samples (X) by mixing two populations drawn from normal distributions with mean values 4 and 12, whose histogram is shown in the upper panel. Dividing this population into 60 equal parts, generates the values marked with orange lines (the *quantiles*). The differences between the quantiles (lower panel) peak at the point that separates the two clusters (break, marked with a red line).

Figure 2 Demonstration on synthetic data of the method of differences of percentiles. Inference of the binary inferred adjacency matrix A^* in the exploratory example using the method of percentiles. The peak in the differences of percentiles (left panel) defines a threshold T that, when used to compute A^* , yields perfect reconstruction (left and right panels). The threshold is shown in the right panel as a thick red line on top of the histogram from Figure 2 in the main text. The method is able to distinguish unbalanced clusters.

References

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